

PROMOTING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EXPERIENCES OF 21ST CENTURY STEM TEACHERS IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

BY

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Abstract

The study was conducted to explore the promotion of inclusive education in Nigerian secondary schools with a focus on 21st century Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) teachers. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were posited and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The mixed method research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in Rivers State with a sample size of 109 STEM teachers obtained using the purposive sampling method. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected using “Structured Interview Template for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Teachers”, “Competency on Inclusive Education Questionnaire” [Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.86$] and adopted instrument of “Multidimensional Attitudes Towards Inclusive Education Scale” (Mahat, 2008). Data was analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation, Analysis of Variance and Scheffe’s Post-hoc test. The findings of the study revealed that STEM teachers level of core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools is at the Average Level of Competence (ALC) [Aggregate Total Mean Value = 2.45, SD = 1.40] and their attitude towards the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools is positive [Aggregate Total Mean Value = 3.30, SD = 1.38]. Empirically, it was proven that there is a significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers’ core competencies and attitude respectively in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools [$F(3,105) = 12.080, p = 0.000$] and [$F(3,105) = 15.058, p = 0.000$]. Based on the findings, the study recommends that there is need for compulsory introduction of inclusive education core competence/attitudinal module in pre-service STEM teacher training programme in tertiary institutions. Refreshers course and trainings for in-service STEM teachers should be conducted on regular basis so that they can be acquainted with the contemporary approach towards inclusive education.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, STEM, Secondary Schools, Teacher, 21st Century.

Introduction

There is no doubt that the fulcrum of national development of any nation is hinged on the implementation of their educational goals, aims and objectives. Issues on educational implementation can never be short changed, as it is the directional compass for revolutionizing science and technology as well as attaining economic stability. While recognizing the importance of education, the Federal

Government of Nigeria as stated in the National Policy on Education (2004) reiterated that “Education in Nigeria is an instrument par excellence for effecting national development”. Therefore, the need to make education all-inclusive is very exigent.

Since the past decades, there have been deliberate drive and consensus efforts by several nations to ensure that the policies and practice of

education in their respective domain is all inclusive. Inclusive education is a form of education that considers and addresses learning needs of all learners specifically to those who are excluded from formal educational settings or marginalized. More recently, Inclusive education has been globally recognized as the pathway for quality education realization for all learners, especially for learners that are traditionally excluded from mainstream education based on the characteristics of disability, ethnicity, gender, giftedness among others (Akawe, 2022).

Ogunode and Yunusa (2022) explained that inclusive education is the process of addressing impediments that hinders the provision of access to quality education by all and meeting their learning needs in the same learning environment. It is a deliberate act of enrolling and placing in schools that are available in the immediate environment of learners irrespective of challenges they may possess, to have access to quality education through extensive assistance and instruction. Inclusive education is drawn on a philosophical belief that every child irrespective of societal characteristics, language, and physical state (physically challenged or non-physically challenged) or emotional conditions should fully participate in learning within the same learning environment. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2005) defined inclusive education as;

“A process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education. This process involves changes and modification in content, approaches, structures and strategies, with a common vision that covers all children of the appropriate age range and a conviction that it is the responsibility of the regular system to educate all children” (p.7)

By extension, the notion of inclusive education does not only guarantee learners with special needs compulsory placement in schools, but it proffer solutions to vast range of human right violations and exclusive practices encountered by special need persons in the area of employment, political aspiration, social elevation as well as cultural implications. Gabel, et al (2009) explained that the exclusion of students with special education needs from regular educational settings does not only reduce learning opportunities, but it provides the avenue for stigmatization and also social exclusion. Historically, there have been several key declarations, manifestos and educational policies provided by several international and local organizations which includes;

- i. United Nations Convention against Discrimination in Education. Paris, France. (1960)
- ii. United Nations Declaration on the Right of Disabled People. (1975)
- iii. United Nations Declaration on the Right of Mentally Retarded Persons. (1971)
- iv. United Nations World Programme of Action 3goals: Concerning Disabled People. (1982)
- v. United Nations Convention on the Right of the Child (CRC). (1989).
- vi. World Declaration on Education for ALL (EFA). (1990)
- vii. UN Standard Rule on Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities. (1993)
- viii. The UNESCO Salamanca Statement and Framework of Action in Special Needs Education, agreed in Salamanca, Spain. (1994).
- ix. Biwako Millennium Framework (BMF) for Action, agreed in Dakar, Senegal.(2000).

Most recently is the United Nations summit on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with

emphases on Goal 4.5.1 in 2019 which focuses on Inclusion and Equity which stipulates that:

“All people, irrespective of sex, age, race, colour, ethnicity, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property or birth, as well as persons with disabilities, migrants, indigenous peoples, and children and youth, especially those in vulnerable situations or other status, should have access to inclusive, equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities.

Dreyer (2017) asserted that most of the declarations advocates the right of every child to receive education without any form of discrimination. While the outcome of conventions set the goal for Education for All, UNESCO Salamanca Statement and Framework of Action in Special Needs Education affirms that all schools are required to accommodate all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions (Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education, 2024). Summarily, the outcome of these conferences provided a template for inclusive education for several governments that is aimed at ensuring adequate implementations. This includes that governments should;

- i. Provide budget priority to enhance educational services that will ensure all children to be included irrespective of their difficulties and differences.
- ii. Deliberately adopt laws that guide enrollment of children into schools in order to implement inclusive education.
- iii. Collaborate with other countries in projects of inclusive education.
- iv. Involve physically challenge and special needs people in decision making concerning their all-round development.

v. Refurbish the teacher education program and school curriculum to accommodate an all-inclusive pedagogy.

vi. Training and retrain teachers to address issues of inclusive education.

Educational policies, manifestos and declarations by various international and national agencies such as United Nations International Children and Emergency Fund (UNICEF) and the United Nation Educational Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), Biwako Millennium Framework (BMF) among others has effected consequential changes in policy approach and practices of educational implementation especially in the developing countries. Notably, the 21st century showcased a tremendous shift in education system, that is, from a general to a more inclusive education, Nigeria was not an exception to this change. Omede (2016) noted that in 1976, there were attempts to ingrain an inclusive education policy during the introduction of the Universal Primary Education in Nigeria. Also, there was the formulation of the first National Policy on Education in 1977 in Nigeria with its document containing special provisions for the equalization of education for all children (Garuba, 2003). More recently, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN,2004) reiterated that;

*“Government has stated that for the benefit of **all** citizens, the country's educational goals shall be clearly set out in terms of their relevance to the needs of the individual and those of the society, in consonance with the realities of our environment and the modern world”.*
(p.4)

Tuggar (2014), Utomo and Thaibah (2021) and Roldán et al (2021) highlighted benefits of implementation of inclusive education. It was mentioned that;

- i. All children will develop a sense of belonging in their various communities.
- ii. Opportunity for enhanced learning.
- iii. Children with varying disability are motivated when learning with other children.
- iv. Efficacious implementation of inclusive education develops strengths and gifts of children with special needs.
- v. There is provision for the opportunity of learning and accepting individual differences.
- vi. It fosters respect and belonging.
- vii. There is opportunity for all children to develop friendship that ensures growth.

If recognizing the values of the diversity and unique contribution as one important key driver of inclusive education, it is therefore imperative that educators in an inclusive classroom should appreciate the fact that all learners irrespective of their physical state, societal characteristics, belief or language must have equal opportunities to receive quality education with optimal capacity to perform without any limitation. Research conducted on inclusive education (Abba & Rashid, 2020; Garrote, Sermier &

Moser 2017) showed that the development of more inclusive classrooms entails that teachers cater for all students learning needs through curriculum differentials, classroom management, attitudinal disposition among others. By implications, the 21st century STEM teachers' competence of the pedagogical processes affect the extent of their abilities to promote inclusive practice in the classroom.

Uniquely, there are set of core values and competence skills expected of 21st century STEM teachers in their effort to implementing inclusive education. Abba and Rashid (2020) commented that such values and competencies set includes the knowledge and skills of teaching strategies and approaches that meet the needs of all children in regular classrooms. These competence set are very vital as they provide the platform for flexibility of classroom instruction, recognition of the reality of difference among the learners while focusing on the adaptation of learning goals, content and learning environment of all learners in the classroom.

Table 1: Core values and competence areas of inclusive teaching.

Core values	Competence areas
Support all learners	Promote academic, practical, social and emotional learning for all Engage effective teaching approaches in heterogeneous classes based on understanding of a variety of learning processes and how to support them
Work with others	Work with parents and families to engage them effectively in learning Work with other education professionals, including collaboration with other teachers
Value learner diversity	Understand inclusive education (e.g. it is based in belief in equality, human rights and democracy for all) Respect, value and view learner diversity as an asset
Engage in professional Development	Be reflective practitioners (i.e. systematically evaluate one's own performance) View initial teacher education as the foundation for ongoing professional learning

Source: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2012)

Singh, Kumar and Singh (2020) viewing beyond competence set opined that it is not enough to prioritize inclusive education as an integral segment of the entire education system, but importance should be placed on teachers' attitude for the inclusion.

Statement of Problem

In recent years, the call for inclusive education has gained significant global attention, emphasizing the need for equitable access to quality education for all learners, regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, or circumstances. In Nigeria, the integration of inclusive pedagogy within Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education remains a

pressing challenge. Despite policies advocating inclusion, many secondary school STEM teachers still lack the core competencies and pedagogical strategies required to accommodate diverse learners in STEM classrooms. This gap often leads to the marginalization of students with learning difficulties or disabilities, thereby undermining the national goal of achieving inclusive and quality education as enshrined in the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). STEM teachers' attitudes play a critical role in the successful implementation of inclusive practices. Negative perceptions, inadequate training, and limited institutional support often hinder teachers' willingness to adopt inclusive approaches in STEM education. In many Nigerian secondary schools, STEM teachers are confronted with large class sizes, inadequate teaching resources and minimal exposure to inclusive instructional models, all of which affect their ability to cater effectively to individual learning needs. Consequently, understanding the experiences, competencies and attitudes of 21st-century STEM teachers toward inclusive pedagogy is essential for identifying gaps and formulating targeted interventions that can foster a more inclusive and equitable learning environment in Nigerian secondary schools.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to explore 21st century STEM teachers' experience on the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools. Specifically, the objectives are to;

- i. Determine the level of STEM teachers' core competencies in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.
- ii. Examine the attitude of STEM teachers in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of STEM teachers' core competencies in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools?
- ii. What is the attitude of STEM teachers in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools?

Hypotheses

- Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers' core competencies in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers' attitude in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.

Methodology

The study adopted the mixed method research design using both quantitative and qualitative research method to provide more depth, clarification and achieving the objectives of the study. The study was conducted in Rivers State, Nigeria. A state located in the South-South geographical terrain of Nigeria. Rivers State lies within latitude 4°45' North and longitude 6°50' East bounded by Abia and Imo States to the North, Bayelsa to the west, AkwaIbom to the east and the Atlantic ocean to the south. The state houses 23 Local Government Areas with an estimated population of 5,198,716 which accounts for 3.7% of the total population in Nigeria (NPC, 2006). The predominant occupations of the people in the state are public service, fishing for those in the riverine areas while farming for those in the upland areas. There are numerous tertiary, secondary and primary institutions in the state that have produced highly trained and skilled individuals in several academic endeavours.

The population of the study consisted of all Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) teachers in all secondary schools in Rivers State. Using purposive

sampling method, 109 STEM teachers were selected for the study. The criteria for selection includes (i) the teachers must be a STEM teacher (ii) must have special needs students in their

class. The distribution of the selected STEM teachers according to subject areas is shown the table below.

Table 2: *Distribution of STEM teachers according to subject area and gender.*

Subject Area	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Science	Male	22	59.5%
	Female	15	40.5%
Total		37	100%
Technology	Male	19	61.3%
	Female	12	38.7%
Total		31	100%
Engineering	Male	13	76.5%
	Female	4	23.5%
Total		17	100%
Mathematics	Male	13	55.9%
	Female	11	44.1%
Total		24	100%

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 2 above shows the distribution of the sampled STEM teachers engaged for the study according to their respective subject areas and gender. A total number of 37 teachers were Science teachers comprising of male 22(59.5%) and female 15(40.5%), Technology teachers selected were 31 consisting of male 19(61.3%) while female were 12(38.7%). Others are 17 Engineering teachers having male 13(76.5%) and female 4(23.5%) and lastly, 24 Mathematics teachers consisting of male 19(55.9%) and female 15(44.1%).

Based on the design adopted for the study, three research instruments were employed to achieve the aim of the study. The instruments were titled “Competency on Inclusive Education Questionnaire” (CIEQ), Multidimensional Attitudes Towards Inclusive Education Scale (MATIES) and “Structured Interview Template for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Teachers” (SIT-STEMT). Competency on Inclusive Education Questionnaire” (CIEQ) was designed to obtain the quantitative data for the study having two sections A and B. Section A considered the

profile data of the participants which includes subject area, gender, academic qualification and years of experience.

Section B specifically focused on the level of STEM teachers’ core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools. There were four parameters that were considered namely

- (i) Instructional parameters
- (ii) Managing disruptive Behaviours
- (iii) Collaborating parameter
- (iv) Evaluation parameter.

Each of these parameters had 5 item statements, making a total of 20 item statement for CIEQ. A modified Likert 5 point scale was adopted to measure quantitatively the core competence of STEM teachers. The scale was categorized as follows;

- High Level of Competence (HLC) = 5 points which denotes extensive experience in the skill area,
- Moderately High Level of Competence (MHLC) = 4 points which denotes good experience in the skill area,

- Average Level of Competence (ALC) = 3 points which denotes some experience in the skill area,
- Low Level of Competence (LLC) = 2 points which denotes little experience in the skill area

- No Level of Competence (NLC) = 1 point which denotes no experience in the skill area
- The quantitative categorization for decision was based on mean value obtained as shown below;

Table 3:

Mean value and level of categorization of STEM teachers' competency on inclusive education.

Mean value	Categorization
0.00 – 1.60	Low Level of Competence (LLC)
1.61 – 3.30	Average Level of Competence (ALC)
.31 – 5.00	High Level of Competence (HLC)

The study adopted the Multidimensional Attitudes Toward Inclusive Education Scale (MATIES) developed by Mahat (2008) which is a 18 item statement survey instrument that has 6 points Likert scale response of Strongly disagree (1) , disagree (2) , somewhat disagree (3), somewhat agree (4), agree (5), and strongly

agree (6) with three multidimensional parameters of cognitive, affective and behavioural. The quantitative categorization for decision for the Multidimensional Attitudes Towards Inclusive Education Scale was based on mean value obtained as shown below;

Table 4:

Mean value and STEM teachers' categorization of attitude to inclusive education.

Mean value	Categorization
0.00 – 2.90	Negative
3.00 – 6.00	Positive

Structured Interview Template for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics Teachers” (SIT-STEMT) was designed to obtain the qualitative data for the study. SIT-STEMT comprises of 6 opened ended structured questions in line with the objectives of the study were posed to the participant of the study to elicit oral response which were very essential and supports their response provided in CIEQ and MATIES. Importantly, informed consent was voluntarily provided by all participating teachers prior to data collection. The interview section was recorded with a digital recorder which lasted for duration of 30 minutes for each participant during the time of the study. The responses

provided by the participants were further transcribed for coding employing the thematic content analysis. This process ensured that patterns of similarities in participant responses were identified.

The researchers gave the instruments to two STEM educators, two Measurement and Evaluation faculty members and two Mass Communicators for their expert views on the face and content validity. Their expert opinions were greatly considered and modifications were made to arrive at a standard instrument. CIEQ was further subjected to a reliability test using the test re-test method employed for duration of

one week. When both data collected was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, a correlation coefficient of 0.86 was obtained making the research instrument CIEQ 86% reliable to be employed for the study. Data

Result

Research Question 1: What is the level of STEM teachers’ core competencies in the

was analyzed using Mean, Standard deviation, Analysis of Variance and Scheffe’s Post-hoc test.

promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools?

Table 5: *STEM Teachers’ response on core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools.*

s/n	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Categorization
1.	Instructional Parameters			
a.	Ability to employ varied instructional approach to enhance knowledge, attitude and skill acquisition in an inclusive classroom.	2.71	1.54	ALC
b.	Ability to select appropriate teaching materials and aids to enhance effective teaching in an inclusive classroom.	2.68	1.49	ALC
c.	Ability to design learning task that take cognizance of individual needs of every learner in an inclusive classroom	2.05	1.63	ALC
d.	Ability to timely identify individual learner’s difficulties during teaching and learning process in an inclusive classroom.	2.20	1.44	ALC
e.	Ability to employ strategic wait time during classroom interaction in an inclusive classroom.	1.94	0.53	ALC
	Aggregate mean value	2.32	1.32	ALC
2.	Managing Disruptive Behaviour			
a.	Ability to identify students’ misbehavior in an inclusive classroom.	2.96	1.49	ALC
b.	Ability to resolve students’ behavior conflicts in an inclusive classroom.	3.01	1.55	ALC
c.	Ability to establish and reinforce positive expectations in an inclusive classroom.	2.22	1.64	ALC
d.	Ability to utilize several anger strategies like positive self-talk, deep breath among others in an inclusive classroom.	2.03	1.50	ALC
e.	Ability to control an inclusive classroom using the non-verbal cues to refocus students’ attention.	2.67	1.64	ALC
	Aggregate mean value	2.58	1.56	ALC
3.	Collaborative Parameters			
a.	Ability to collaborate with colleagues to enhance quality teaching in an inclusive classroom.	2.67	1.61	ALC
b.	Positively collaborating with parents whose child(ren) has special needs.	2.40	1.55	ALC
c.	Capacity to collaborate with other professional in designing educational programmes/plans for inclusive education.	2.00	1.48	ALC
d.	Deliberating seeking professional help and advice in advancing effective teaching and learning in an inclusive classroom.	2.38	1.57	ALC
e.	Ability to collaborate with Non-Governmental Organization for support in enhancing effective learning experience for inclusive education.	1.58	1.50	ALC
		2.21	1.54	ALC

Aggregate mean value				
4.	Evaluation Parameters			
a.	Knowledge of various evaluation instrument constructions for inclusive education.	2.43	1.51	ALC
b.	Collecting and interpreting data to identify students' learning difficulties and way for improvement.	2.22	1.53	ALC
c.	Ability to provide formative evaluation during teaching and learning in an inclusive classroom.	2.60	0.44	ALC
d.	Ability to access learners' psychomotor, affective and cognitive skills in an inclusive classroom.	3.11	0.85	ALC
e.	Knowledge of students' performance and grade record keeping in an inclusive classroom.	3.00	1.56	ALC
	Aggregate mean value	2.67	1.18	ALC
	Aggregate Total Mean Value	2.45	1.40	ALC

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025. * ALC (Average Level of Competence)

The result in the analysis as shown in Table 5 provides STEM Teachers' response on core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools. It was revealed that the core competencies of STEM teachers with respect to instructional parameters was at Average Level of Competence (ALC) at [Aggregate mean value = 2.32, SD = 1.32]. Considering STEM teachers' level of competence in managing disruptive behavior, the result shows an [Aggregate mean value = 2.58, SD = 1.56] indicating an Average Level of Competence (ALC). Furthermore, STEM teachers' level of competency promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools was

also ascertained focusing on collaborative parameters. An [Aggregate mean value = 2.21, SD = 1.54] was obtained indicating Average Level of Competence (ALC). The study at the level of evaluation parameters indicated that STEM teachers had Average Level of Competence (ALC) as shown by the [Aggregate mean value = 2.67, SD = 1.18]. The findings of the study therefore reveals that STEM teachers level of core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools is at the Average Level of Competence (ALC) [Aggregate Total Mean Value = 2.45, STDv = 1.40].

Research Question 2: What is the attitude of STEM teachers in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools?

Table 6: *STEM Teachers’ responses on attitude towards the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools.*

S/N	Cognitive			
1.	I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.	3.68	0.98	Positive
2.	I do not believe that students with a disability should be taught only in special education schools.	3.59	1.17	Positive
3.	I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior amongst all students.	2.26	0.87	Negative
4.	I believe that any student can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.	2.14	1.61	Negative
5.	I do not believe that students with a disability should be segregated because it is too expensive to modify the physical environment of the school.	3.33	1.50	Positive
6.	I do not believe that students with a disability should be in special education schools so that they do not experience rejection in the regular school.	3.57	1.42	Positive
Aggregate mean value		3.10	1.26	Positive
Affective				
7.	I do not have difficulty communicating with students with a disability.	3.07	1.58	Positive
8.	I am very satisfied when students with a disability keep up with the day-to-day curriculum in my classroom.	3.21	1.49	Positive
9.	I am able to understand students with a disability.	3.00	1.55	Positive
10.	I am comfortable including students with a disability in a regular classroom with other students without a disability.	3.18	0.99	Positive
11.	I am disconcerted that students with a disability are included in the regular classroom, regardless of the severity of the disability.	3.14	1.53	Positive
12.	I am willing to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students.	3.23	1.62	Positive
Aggregate mean value		3.14	1.46	Positive
Behavioural				
13.	I am willing to encourage students with a disability to participate in all social activities in the regular classroom.	3.60	1.45	Positive
14.	I am willing to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students regardless of their ability.	3.69	0.81	Positive
15.	I am willing to physically include students with a severe disability in the regular classroom with the necessary support.	3.55	1.66	Positive
16.	I am willing to modify the physical environment to include students with a disability in the regular classroom.	3.66	1.51	Positive
17.	I am willing to adapt my communication techniques to ensure that all students with an emotional and behavioural disorder can be successfully included in the regular classroom.	3.81	1.56	Positive
18.	I am willing to adapt the assessment of individual students in order for inclusive education to take place.	3.73	1.50	Positive
Aggregate mean value		3.67	1.42	Positive
Aggregate Total Mean Value		3.30	1.38	Positive

Source: Researchers’ Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 6 shows the analysis of STEM teachers’ responses on attitude that cut across three important features that includes cognitive, affective and behavior geared towards the

promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools. The result indicated that the attitude of STEM teachers towards the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools in the cognitive feature as an aggregate mean value of 3.10, SD = 1.26 indicating a positive attitude.

Also, an aggregate mean value of 3.14, SD = 1.46 showing a positive attitude of STEM teachers in the affective features. STEM teachers' response on the behavioural features revealed a positive attitude with aggregate mean value of 3.67, SD = 1.42. The findings of the study therefore revealed that the attitude of STEM teachers in the promotion of inclusive

education in secondary schools is positive [Aggregate Total Mean Value = 3.30, SD = 1.38].

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers' core competencies in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.

Table 7: Showing Analysis of Variance of STEM teachers' core competencies mean values in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2553.515	3	851.172	12.080	.000
Within Groups	7398.596	105	70.463		
Total	9952.110	108			

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 7 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of STEM teachers' core competencies mean values in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools. It was revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers' core competencies in the promotion of inclusive

pedagogy in secondary schools $F(3,105) = 12.080, p = 0.000$. Further analysis of Multiple Comparisons using the Scheffe's post-hoc test was employed to ascertain the margin of difference between the mean.

Table 8: Showing Scheffe's post-hoc analysis between STEM teachers' core competencies mean values in the promotion of inclusive pedagogy in secondary schools.

Groups	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Technology teachers	31	27.8065	
Engineering teachers	18	28.2778	
Science teachers	37		37.5405
Mathematics teachers	23		37.9565
Sig.		.998	.999

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025.

Analysis on Table 8 presents the post-hoc analysis of marginal mean difference of STEM teacher score competencies mean values in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools. The result indicated that Mathematics teachers had the highest mean value of 37.9565, which was followed by Science teachers with a mean value of 37.5405. Engineering teachers and Technology teachers had mean values of 28.2776 and 27.8065 respectively. The findings

of the study therefore revealed that Mathematics teachers has the most core competence in promoting inclusive education in secondary schools, followed by Science teachers, Engineering teachers and technology teachers.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers' attitude in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools.

Table 9: Showing Analysis of Variance of STEM teachers’ attitude mean values in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6398.207	3	2132.736	15.058	.000
Within Groups	14872.105	105	141.639		
Total	21270.312	108			

Source: Researchers’ Fieldwork, 2025.

Table 9 shows the ANOVA output of STEM teachers’ attitude mean values in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools. The result indicated that there is significant difference between the mean values of STEM teachers’ attitude in the promotion of inclusive

education in secondary schools $F(3,105) = 15.058, p = 0.000$. The Multiple Comparison test using the Scheffe’s post-hoc test was employed to determine margin of difference between the mean.

Table 10: Showing Scheffe’s post-hoc analysis between STEM teachers’ attitude mean values in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools.

Groups	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Science teachers	37	27.8108	
Engineering teachers	17	28.1765	
Technology teachers	31	37.0000	
Mathematics teachers	24		47.2083
Sig.		.065	1.000

Source: Researchers’ Fieldwork, 2025.

The post-hoc test conducted to determine the marginal mean values of STEM teachers’ response on their attitude towards the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools shows that Mathematics teachers had the highest mean value of 47.2 while Technology teachers had a mean value of 37.0. Engineering teachers had a mean value of 28.2 while a mean value of 27.8 was obtained for Science teachers which are the least.

Discussion of Findings

The study was concerned with exploring the promotion of inclusive Education in Nigeria secondary schools focusing on 21st century STEM teachers’ competence and attitude. Crick (2008) stated that teacher competence for inclusive education is defined as being a complex combination of knowledge, skills and attitude that allow a teacher to successfully respond to pupils’ diversity in the classroom. The

findings of the study reveal that STEM teachers’ level of core competencies in the promotion of inclusive education in secondary schools is at the Average Level of Competence. The result of this study is in agreement with the findings of Nimante and Kokare (2022) where it was mentioned that teachers indicated that they have a slightly higher level of general competence; however, there is room for improvement in both general and specific competencies for inclusive education.

Supporting the research findings is the study of Martikai, Salim, and Yusuf (2016) titled, Understanding level of regular teachers’ competency in inclusive school: a study on pedagogy competency understanding to children with special needs in inclusive school. In that study, it was revealed that regular teachers’ pedagogy competency of inclusive education shows that most regular teachers in inclusive school have low pedagogy competency for

inclusive education. Gunarhadiaet. al. (2016) also showed in their study on pedagogic mapping of teacher competence in inclusive schools that teachers in inclusive schools had inadequate knowledge on instruction for children with special needs and possesses limited teaching skills while teaching heterogeneous class.

Collaborating with the findings of this study is the research outcome of Mohanasundaram (2020) where it was expressed that the competency of the teachers working across the school level to provide inclusive education for children is found to be near 50% which is at average level. However, contrary to the findings of the study, is the observation of Durdukoca (2021) where it was noted that the professional competencies of participating teachers regarding inclusive education are at a very high level. Excerpts from the participants interviewed on STEM teachers revealed that;

“Teaching in a heterogeneous classroom is a unique adventure because you are expected to create a learning environment such that all learners irrespective of any disability must be able to understand the lesson.” (T₉)

“Resourcefulness is the key word....., the teaching and learning approach must involve audio-visual-kinesthetic features. It works”. (T₁₅)

Inclusive classroom room is quite tasking, you must identify individual learner’s difficulties, design instructional packages that will enhance effective classroom interaction”. (T₂)

“I am very conscious and flexible in my motivational approach during teaching because to reduce or completely manage disruptive behavior your set induction must be apt while extending positive praise to learners that conduct themselves in class”. (T₅)

“There are some students that must be at the front row, they are very hyperactive, some visual impaired. We teachers are expected to identify these issues to curtail excessive behaviours in class”. (T₁₃)

In an inclusive classroom, teachers require a diverse set of competencies to effectively support the learning and development of all students, regardless of their abilities, backgrounds, or differences. Effective STEM teachers must be both knowledgeable and

inventive. They are to have good skills in transferring knowledge by developing strategies aimed at equipping all learners. They must also be capable of inventing new strategies. Managing disruptive behavior in an inclusive classroom requires a combination of proactive motivational strategies, consistent implementation of classroom rules and routines, positive behavior reinforcement, and individualized support for students. Some participant interviewed noted that;

“I am very conscious and flexible in my motivational approach during teaching because to reduce or completely manage disruptive behavior your set induction must be apt while extending positive praise to learners that conduct themselves in class”. (T₁₂)

“There are some students that must be at the front row, they are very hyperactive, some visual impaired. We teachers are expected to identify these issues to curtail excessive behaviours in class”. (T₁₃)

“For me, I set clear and specific behavior expected from my students from the commencement of my class which they must write down”. (T₂₁)

“I clearly inform the students of the consequences for any form of disruptive behavior which consistently apply”. (T₈)

Rafi et al., (2020) submits that the intervention strategies that are essential in combating discipline issues in the classroom should include praising, motivating, or reinforcing students while maintaining a positive close relationship with students. It is also necessary to formulate basic classroom rules at the beginning of the courses; adapting student-centered learning, and frequently changing the seating arrangements. In that light, Wong and Wong (2014) opined that the utmost importance of any inclusive classroom is that STEM teachers must create a learning environment that is aptly managed with clear instructions and routine that is understandable to the learners. There was a large extent of similarities in response of the

participants on the implementation of evaluation parameters as means of STEM teachers' competence in promoting inclusive education in secondary schools. The major response was observed was the use of formative assessment approach especially during classroom interactions.

The study also investigated STEM teachers' attitude towards the promotion of inclusive education in secondary school and the findings revealed that STEM teachers' attitude was positive. In agreement with the present study, Galaterou (2017) explained that teachers demonstrated marginally positive attitudes towards inclusion. Kazmi, Kanram and Siddiqui (2023) in their study of the effect of teacher's attitudes in supporting inclusive education by catering to diverse learners indicated that the results from the structural equation modeling analysis revealed that teachers have positive attitudes toward the education of children in an inclusive setting. Also, congruence to the study is the outcome of the study of Ediyanto and Kawai (2023) that showed that teachers' attitude towards inclusive education in East Java, Indonesia was positive and a major factor that influences that positive approach was the school level where the teachers work. Igbokwe, Mezieobi and Eke (2014) in their study noted that secondary school teachers in Owerri Education zone have positive attitude and views towards inclusive education. Excerpt from some participant interviewed indicated that;

As a science teacher for the past 18 years, I have taught several students with special needs in this classroom and I must tell you, you must be patient and inventive employing several teaching approach. (T₂₂) I don't think students with special need should not be in the same classroom with others, I have encountered such experience. Such students in my class performed very well. (T₄). I approach such class with flexibility mindset. Engage them actively during class activity using collaborative approach...most times kids with

special needs are team leaders, you will active positive results. (T₁₃) Assessment approach is quite different in heterogeneous classroom. Learners with special needs require individualized formative process in achieving better performance. (T₆)

Inclusive education is a dynamic approach that seeks to integrate all students, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, into the general education system. It is predicated on the belief that every child has the right to a quality education and that schools should be designed to accommodate diverse learning needs. STEM teachers' role is to focus their duties within the inclusion practices that encompass the alignment of the goals of the inclusive education policy.

Conclusion

Inclusive education represents a paradigm shift in the way we approach learning and teaching. By embracing diversity and focusing on equity, inclusive education not only supports the academic and social development of students with disabilities but also enriches the educational experience for all learners. While challenges exist, they can be addressed through strategic planning, professional development, positive attitude and commitment in creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment. Ultimately, inclusive education fosters a more just and compassionate society, preparing students to thrive in a world where diversity is the norm and every individual's potential is valued and nurtured.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations were made;

1. There is need for compulsory introduction of inclusive education core competence/attitudinal module in pre-service STEM teacher training programme in tertiary institutions.
2. Refreshers course and trainings for in-service STEM teachers should be conducted

on regular basis so that they can be acquainted with the contemporary approach towards inclusive education.

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